

Clinical Pharmacist-Driven Education and Its Impact on Medication Behaviour in Haemodialysis Patients: A Prospective Cross-Sectional Analysis

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Received: Jul 25, 2025

Accepted: Aug 14, 2025

Published: Aug 25, 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: Haemodialysis patients often require complex medication regimens and renal replacement therapy (RRT) for managing comorbid conditions as well as chronic kidney disease (CKD). Adherence to the prescribed medications, RRT as well as to the fluid and dietary restrictions is important for preventing disease progression. Poor medication adherence and lack of medication knowledge can have a negative impact on the treatment outcome.

Method: A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care teaching

hospital, including patients receiving regular haemodialysis between 18 and 80 years old. Initially, validated questionnaires were used to gather the baseline data on medication knowledge and medication adherence. The patients then received counselling regarding the significance of adhering to the medication, haemodialysis, and to dietary and fluid restrictions. Moreover, they were educated about their medications. 2nd and 3rd follow-ups were done with an interval of 15 days and responses to the questionnaires were noted and subsequent patient education and counselling were given.

Result: The study included a total of 111 haemodialysis patients. A significant improvement in the medication knowledge scores was seen from baseline to the second follow-up. The medication adherence scores also showed a notable increase from baseline to the second follow-up. However, the association between medication knowledge and adherence was not found to be statistically significant.

Conclusion:

Statistically significant improvement in medication adherence and medication knowledge scores from baseline to the 2nd follow-up demonstrated that clinical pharmacist intervention had a positive impact in improving medication knowledge and adherence levels in haemodialysis patients.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease, Clinical pharmacist, Medication adherence, Medication knowledge, Haemodialysis

INTRODUCTION

Gradual and irreversible alterations in kidney structure and/or function are hallmarks of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Patients presented with a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) less than 60 ml/min/1.7 m², accompanied by signs of renal injury like albuminuria, haematuria, persistent electrolyte disturbances, abnormalities in renal imaging and histological changes in kidney biopsy for 3 months or more are diagnosed with CKD¹. Owing to the rising incidence of the aging population and increasing prevalence of obesity, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus, the problem has reached epidemic proportions. Regardless of the underlying etiology, chronic renal failure inevitably results in irreversible nephron loss, end-stage renal disease, and possibly early mortality. Reduced kidney regeneration ability, fibrosis, chronic inflammation, and loss of parenchymal cells are among the progression factors².

A comprehensive approach is necessary to manage CKD which prioritizes on slowing the disease progression, treating complications such as anaemia, mineral and bone disorders, electrolyte imbalances, metabolic acidosis, and cardiovascular disease, and sensitizing patients for renal replacement therapy (RRT). It is also essential to establish a comprehensive immunization regimen, specifically for hepatitis B¹. The decision to initiate dialysis in CKD patients is based on the presence of clinical symptoms and deranged laboratory data^{1,3}. A multifaceted approach involving RRT, medications, fluid, and diet restrictions is required for the management of CKD. Due to their extremely complicated treatment regimen dialysis patients are regarded as a special patient population⁴. Hence

collaboration among healthcare providers like physicians, clinical pharmacists, nurses, nutrition experts, and psychologists plays a crucial role in managing this condition.

Managing CKD, which is frequently accompanied by additional comorbid conditions such as diabetes and hypertension, requires careful attention to medication adherence and medication knowledge^{5,6}. Knowing the name, indication, dosage schedule, side effects, and administration instructions of the drug is considered as medication knowledge. This knowledge plays pivotal role in maximizing the medication adherence⁵. Medication adherence is defined as the extent to which a patient's behaviour aligns with the prescriber's recommendations. Poor adherence to the prescribed medication regimen can compromise patient safety, can lead to increased hospital admissions, and ultimately lower quality of life (QOL). Patients are bound to follow the prescriptions when they know about the outcomes of not doing so⁷.

Medication Knowledge Assessment Questionnaire (MKAQ) is one of the several approved questionnaires designed to evaluate patients' medication knowledge. The patient's ability to remember the name, indication, dose, and side effects of the medications they take are assessed through this questionnaire⁸. More importantly, these patients could have several misconceptions about their medications, which can be resolved with the help of routine health examinations and counselling sessions^{7,9}. Hence, imparting medication knowledge to the patients can promote medication adherence⁷.

Patient-related characteristics such as age, gender, education, health beliefs, and socioeconomic status can influence

nonadherence. Apart from this, psychological aspects like stress, depression, and irrational thoughts also influence nonadherence. Limited access to treatment and financial restraints can further complicate the situation and result in nonadherence¹⁰. Greek simplified medication adherence questionnaire- haemodialysis (GR-SMAQ-HD) is exclusively used to measure adherence to the treatment in haemodialysis patients. This questionnaire is categorized into 3 subscales which measures the adherence to medication, dialysis, and fluid/diet. The primary benefit of this questionnaire is to identify particular domains of patient's nonadherence, enabling tailored therapies¹¹. Early detection of non-adherence is important for better health outcomes in HD patients. Healthcare professionals can enhance adherence and lower associated risks by assessing drug knowledge and offering focused instruction, resulting in more efficient treatment management^{7,8}.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Study design and study site:

A prospective cross-sectional study was carried out in the haemodialysis unit of a tertiary care hospital in India for a duration of 6 months. The study was registered in the Clinical Trial Registry of India.

Inclusion criteria:

Male and female haemodialysis patients of age group 18 to 80 years were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients getting therapy for depression or those with a diagnosis of psychiatric disorder were not permitted to partake in the trial. The study did not include patients with advanced malignancy, participants with hearing disability or visual impairment, women who

were pregnant or nursing, and people who chose not to give consent.

Ethical considerations:

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee for the study prior to its commencement.

Intervention:

Considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the patients with chronic kidney disease who were on haemodialysis treatment at a tertiary care teaching hospital were chosen. Details regarding the ongoing study were explained to the subjects in their native language and their queries regarding the same were clarified. Informed consent forms were given to the patients who communicated their readiness to take part in the study. Once the patient gave consent to partake in the study their demographic details and questionnaire replies were recorded. At first, the baseline data was gathered by Pharm D interns who evaluated the drug knowledge and medication adherence of patients who came to the dialysis unit for their scheduled dialysis sessions. After that, the patients had 15 to 30 minutes of counselling about their condition, the medications that were recommended, and the significance of adhering to food and hydration guidelines. Furthermore, a patient information pamphlet was used to aid in patient education. Additionally, during this interactive session, patients were urged to take their prescribed medications as directed and to abide by the food and fluid recommendations. At the same time, patient's doubts regarding their medications were also cleared. Later on, the first and second follow-ups were conducted 15 days apart, during which the responses were documented and subsequent patient counselling and patient education were provided. The responses were then analysed.

Study instrument:

The medication adherence of HD patients was assessed using the Greek Simplified Medication Adherence Questionnaire-Haemodialysis (GR-SMAQ-HD). This questionnaire was solely used to measure the adherence of HD to their treatment. It included 8 items which were sorted into 3 subscales such as medication adherence, attendance at haemodialysis sessions, and fluid/ diet. Simultaneously, the Medication Knowledge Assessment Questionnaire (MKAQ) was utilized to gauge the medication knowledge of these patients. This questionnaire comprised of 10 questions.

Sample size:

111 haemodialysis patients with chronic renal disease were included in the study. The sample size was calculated with a 7% allowed risk and a 95% confidence interval.

Statistical analysis:

The data was analysed using the SPSS version 26. The data was expressed as mean and standard deviation. Medication knowledge was expressed as percentages, showing the dispersion of patients across poor, good, and excellent categories at each time point. Medication knowledge and medication adherence at baseline, 1st follow-up, and 2nd follow-up were compared using paired t-tests. The p-value <0.05 is considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Over the period of 6 months, a total of 111 CKD patients who visited the haemodialysis unit were reviewed. Based on the demographic data, the study participants were largely male consisting of 68.5% (76) whereas 31.5% (35) were female. In terms of age distribution, it was found that most of the study participants were those aged 58 years and above which made up 55.9% (62) of the

total population. Then again, patients aged between 18 – 27 years constituted the smallest proportion, accounting for only 3.6% (4) of the participants. Approximately 76.5% (85) of the study participants were unemployed. Further, the distribution of comorbidities revealed that 12.6% (14) of the study participants had no comorbidities whereas 40.5% (45) of the subjects had hypertension as a comorbidity and 34.2% (38) of the subjects had both hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus.

BASELINE CHARACTERS	FREQUENCY (%)
Age	
18-27	4 (3.6)
28-37	8 (7.2)
38-47	9 (8.1)
48-57	28 (25.2)
≥58	62 (55.9)
Gender	
Male	76 (68.5)
Female	35 (31.5)
Occupation	
Employed	65 (58.6)
Unemployed	46 (41.4)
Comorbidity	
NIL	14 (12.6)
HYPERTENSION	45 (40.5)
TYPE 2 DM	5 (4.5)
HTN+TYPE 2 DM	38 (34.2)
HTN+IHD	2 (1.8)
Others	7 (6.3)

Table 1: Distribution of patients based on demographic characters

Figure 1 demonstrates the improvement in the medication knowledge scores between baseline and follow-ups. The mean medication knowledge score at baseline was 6.64 which increased to 8.46 during the first follow-up. It further improved to 9.34 at the second follow-up indicating improvement in patients' medication knowledge over time.

The distribution of patients according to medication knowledge is shown in Table 2. At baseline, 15.31% of patients had poor medication knowledge, 51.35% had good medication knowledge, and 33.3% had excellent medication knowledge. During the first follow-up, the individuals with poor medication knowledge were reduced to 0% and the proportion of patients with excellent medication knowledge increased to 75.6%. Additionally, the second follow-up witnessed a rise in the percentage of patients with excellent medication knowledge to 98.2%.

Fig 1: Progression of medication knowledge scores from baseline to second follow-ups.

Medication Knowledge	Baseline	First follow-up	Second follow-up
Poor	17 (15.31%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Good	57 (51.35%)	27 (24.32%)	2 (1.8%)
Excellent	37 (33.3%)	84 (75.6%)	109 (98.2%)

Table 2: Distribution of patients based on medication knowledge

Table 3 indicates the comparison of medication knowledge scores at different time points. A statistically significant increase in medication knowledge was seen from baseline to the first follow-up with a p-value < 0.001. Similarly, a comparison of medication knowledge scores between the first follow-up and second follow-up as well as between baseline and second follow-up disclosed a statistically significant difference with a p-value<0.001. The above data suggest that the intervention implemented during this study was effective in improving the medication knowledge of haemodialysis patients.

Figure 2 illustrates the progression of the mean medication adherence score over 3 time points. The mean scores exhibited a positive trend, rising from baseline (5.98±1.635) to the first follow-up (7.24±1.064), and further

increasing at the second follow-up (7.77±0.583).

Medication Knowledge	Mean	SD	p-value
Baseline	6.63	1.75	p<0.001*
First follow up	8.46	1.24	
Baseline	6.63	1.75	p<0.001*
Second follow up	9.34	0.83	
First follow up	8.46	1.24	p<0.001*
Second follow up	9.34	0.83	

Table 3: Comparison of Medication Knowledge at different time points

Fig 2: Progression of Medication Adherence score from baseline to second follow-up

Table 4 represents the comparison of adherence of the HD patients to the treatment provided across different time points, it highlights improvements in 3 key areas: medication adherence, attendance at haemodialysis sessions, and fluid/ diet adherence. Medication adherence demonstrated a notable increase from baseline to the first follow-up ($p=0.006$) and from the first follow-up to the second follow-up ($p<0.001$). However, the improvement in the medication adherence score between the baseline and the second follow-up was not

statistically significant ($p=0.85$) indicating that earlier improvements may have plateaued. When attendance at the haemodialysis session is considered, there was indeed a statistically significant improvement from baseline to first follow-up ($p<0.001$) and from baseline to second follow-up ($p<0.001$), but there was no significant change between first and second follow-up. Lastly, the study found consistent and statistically significant improvements in fluid/diet adherence from baseline to first follow-up ($p<0.001$), from the first follow-up to the second follow-up ($p<0.001$), and from baseline to the second follow-up ($p<0.001$).

MA Domain	Time points	Absolute mean difference	p-value
Medication Adherence	Baseline- First follow-up	0.3	$p=0.006$
	First follow up- Second follow up	0.3	$p< 0.001^{***}$
	Baseline-Second follow-up	0.0	$p=0.85$
Attendance at Haemodialysis Session	Baseline- First follow-up	0.2	$p< 0.001^{***}$
	First follow up- Second follow up	0.0	$p=0.7$
	Baseline-Second follow-up	0.2	$p< 0.001^{***}$
Fluid/Diet	Baseline- First follow-up	0.3	$p< 0.001^{***}$
	First follow up- Second follow up	0.3	$p< 0.001^{***}$
	Baseline-Second follow-up	0.6	$p< 0.001^{***}$

Table 4: Comparison of Adherence to treatment at different time points

DISCUSSION:

In patients with CKD, renal impairment has been observed for longer than three months. Since it can affect waste removal, fluid, and electrolyte balance these patients might eventually require renal replacement therapy to manage the condition. Also, since this group of patients have various comorbid conditions, they are typically prescribed multiple medications. Medication knowledge and adherence are interconnected so poor medication knowledge may negatively impact patient safety and medication adherence, leading to frequent hospital visits.

When the demographic characteristics are considered a notable proportion of the subjects, which is about 68.5% (76) of the study participants were men, while 31.5% (35) were women. This is in line with the findings of the study conducted by **Rani et al. (2013)** and contrasts with the study led by **Mirzaei et al. (2022)** where females dominated the CKD population. Further majority of the patients in our study, about 55.9% belonged to the age group of 58 years and older. These results line up with the perceptions of the research work carried out by **Mailani et al., (2024)** thereby indicating that CKD is more prevalent in older individuals. Among the study participants, a notable proportion of the patients 76.5% (85) were unemployed. Additionally, the trends of comorbidities in these patients revealed that a significant percentage of 40.5% (45) of the patients had hypertension as a comorbidity whereas 34.2% (38) of the study subjects had both hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus as a comorbidity.

Aggarwal et al., (2018) in a study demonstrated that patients who were from higher socio-economic backgrounds and patients who had higher basic education were

likely to be proficient about their condition as well as their management, which enabled them to adhere to the treatment plans in a better way. Conversely, our study tracked down no significant connection between education and medication knowledge or between income and medication adherence of haemodialysis patients. Additionally, a study by **Alkatheri et al. (2014)** demonstrated better adherence levels in elderly patients ($p = 0.012$) alongside married individuals ($p = 0.012$). Contrary to this, there was null association between medication adherence and age or marital status. Our study results showed a significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) in Medication Knowledge from baseline to second follow-up. It is consistent with a previous study by **Baby et al. (2017)** which demonstrated significant improvement in patient's knowledge ($p < 0.05$) after providing education to the patients and thereby decreasing misconceptions about the condition. Approximately 58 (52.2%) patients in our study were unaware of the name of the medication they were prescribed. **Romero-Sanchez et al. (2016)** found that not knowing the name of their prescription was one of the characteristics linked to adult patients' insufficient medication knowledge. Additionally, when adherence to the treatment is considered medication adherence and attendance to the haemodialysis session showed significant improvement from baseline to first follow-up. Conversely, fluid and diet adherence showed significant betterment across all time points. These results resonate with the study conducted by **Jain et al. (2018)**, which also indicated a statistically significant increase in the mean adherence score from baseline to follow-up. In our study, the association between medication knowledge and medication adherence was found to be non-significant. This is in contrast to **Aggarwal et al. (2018)**,

which found a statistically significant association ($p = 0.005$) between medication knowledge and adherence.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, we concluded that in haemodialysis patients there was a considerable gap in the knowledge about their medication regimen, especially among patients who had recently started on haemodialysis. It was out shown that there was a lack of adherence to prescribed medications, diet/fluid recommendations, and attendance at the haemodialysis session. This insufficient knowledge about the prescribed medications and lack of adherence to the treatment regimen can lead to various health hazards, which marks a prominent reason for their frequent hospitalization. The intervention delivered by the clinical pharmacist played a sophisticated role in addressing these challenges. Detailed patient education imparted to the patients addressed a number of topics including indication of the medicines, how to handle missed doses, side effects, information about the food and drugs to be avoided while taking certain medications, benefits of taking these medications, and storage instructions. Importantly the patients were counselled regarding the importance of adhering to the medications, diet/ fluid restrictions, and haemodialysis sessions. They were additionally provided with an explanation of how non-adherence to the treatment regimen leads to exacerbation of their conditions. There were multiple benefits from this comprehensive education. The first one being, that it equipped patients with the necessary knowledge to control their illness better and actively participate in their own care. Secondly, it made it simpler for people to distinguish between symptoms brought on by their illness and adverse drug reactions,

allowing them to discuss the issue with corresponding healthcare professionals more precisely. Thirdly, it stressed how crucial it is to follow calorie restrictions and restricted meals, both of which are critical for tackling their illness. The study demonstrated an increasing trend in medication knowledge and medication adherence scores following the intervention. Interventions offered by clinical pharmacists were therefore successful in enhancing patient outcomes, lowering complications, and ensuring the more effective overall management of their condition.

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How to cite this article: Vinaya Baji, Keerthana P Melanta, Sajan Francis P, Thanveer Ahammed Chonari, Vineetha K, Padmaja Udaykumar. Clinical Pharmacist-Driven Education and its Impact on Medication Behaviour in Haemodialysis Patients: A Prospective Cross-Sectional Analysis. *JDUT* 2025;32:8:636-644